

Graduates' destination of the Bachelor of Multimedia Arts at St. Dominic College of Asia, Academic Years 2014 to 2016

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Abstract

This study engages in a destination survey of the graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts of St. Dominic College of Asia for Academic Years 2014-2016. This research study utilized a descriptive research design to provide specific answers associated with the problem specified in this paper. Twenty (20) respondents participated in this study as the graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts. The study showed that all employed graduates are currently working with jobs related to fields of Multimedia Arts. Furthermore, most of the respondents said their current job is their first job after college, and most of them considered their salary or benefits as one of the key factors on why they chose to stay on their current job followed by career challenge and related skills. The study also showed that salary and benefits influenced the respondents on why they chose to find another job, followed by career challenge. On the other hand, respondents said that they only stayed for about half a year to two (2) years in their first job before leaving. Among the skills learned in college, the respondents found communication skills as one of the most useful skills learned in college followed by Critical-thinking, Human Relations, and Creative Skills. It is recommended that the institution should focus and organize more job fair activities for the students of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts since the findings showed that one of the most determining factors in finding their jobs was through advertisements.

Keywords: Graduates' destination, tracer study, Bachelor of Multimedia Arts.

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Introduction

Education is one of the most important factors in the development of an individual. It professionally hones and develops people and equips them with professional skills and knowledge which they must imbibe and practice in their chosen field. Moreover, education is very important because it allows individuals to be prepared with the demands of industries and allows them to acquire experiential learning and skills essential in the pursuit of employment.

This study traced back the graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts and discussed the factors that affected the graduates in job hunting and getting. This also discussed the skills and knowledge of which they were able to acquire during college studies and whether those skills are useful or not in their chosen professional career.

With these realities that affront them, St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA) has offered several programs for the past fourteen years. Currently, there are seventeen (17) programs that are being offered. In view of this, the Bachelor of Multimedia Arts, which was first offered in the Academic Year 2013-2014 produced numerous batches of graduates for the past years.

In today's modern time, the Bachelor of Multimedia Arts is one of the most sought-after programs taken by college students. In studies conducted by Castillo (2012) and Comunian et al. (2015), fields related with design were considered as one of the highest paying jobs, not only in the Philippines but also around the world. With the continuous development and need of the community for multimedia artists and designers, a necessity to consider various specializations in the field of multimedia should be underscored. This is a great step to cope up with the demands of industries for artists and designers in specific fields of multimedia.

The program, being one of the most in-demand fields by corporations in the industries, focused on the different fields of multimedia. The term "multi" came from the word various, and on the other hand, the term "media" refers to the different modes of communication. Furthermore, the program "Multimedia Arts" refers to the different modes of communication with the application of some aesthetic and creative qualities.

Moreover, what motivated the researcher in conducting this study is the eagerness to find out the responsiveness and effectiveness of the graduates and the program which can be measured primarily on the employment rate of the students who were able to complete the program. This aimed to trace the graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts of St. Dominic College of Asia, to gather feedback, and to seek for present information about their demographic profile, employment-related information, and other skill relevant data (Amante & Mamangon, 2018; Panis, 2015; Virata, 2020).

According to Schomberg (2016), a tracer study can be defined as a standardized graduate survey, which may come in oral or written form, and which takes place sometime after graduation or training, which aims to gather a diverse set of data, come of which are study progress, transition to work, work entrance, and job career, among others.

On a deeper perspective, a tracer study primarily aims to gather information from the graduates of a specific program relevant to the needs of an educational institution, such of these are job or employment related data and study progress. Data gathered is a key information in identifying the responsiveness and effectiveness of the program. It is also an effective tool in evaluating the program and its curriculum which can then be used for continuously enhancing the program itself (Dusaran, 2008; Zembere & Chinyama, 2013).

Verona (2011) conducted a tracer study about the graduates of Polytechnic University of the Philippines Main Campus – Quezon City. The study was composed of fifty (50) respondents. On a general analysis about the demographic and employment profile of the respondents, majority of which are females and are residing at National Capital Region (NCR). Majority of the respondents are non-takers or passers of any professional licensure exams, in relation to most respondents as Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurial Management (BSEM) degree holders, and only one of the respondents pursued post-studies examination. With regards to the employment profile of the 50 respondents, 30 or sixty percent (60%) are regular/permanent employees, six (6) or twelve percent (12%) are contractual, and four (4) or eight percent (8%) are unemployed and temporary, respectively.

Through the results of the study, it was recommended that the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), together with the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), should encourage graduates to take the professional licensure examination in relation to their degree for them to land a more eligible type of job. It was also recommended that the PUPQC officials should conduct seminars, symposium, and trainings to the graduating students focusing in finding jobs after college.

Moreover, a tracer study conducted by Rocaberte (2010) showed that out of the 500 respondents from the graduates of the University of Pangasinan, which was equally distributed from different degree programs covered by the Academic Year 2001-2004, only 75 percent (75%) are employed. Both Bachelor of Arts and Bachelor of Science in Nursing registered the highest number of employed graduates of eighty-three percent (83%). On the other hand, Architecture, Management Accounting, and Physical Therapy got the lowest number of employed graduates reaching only sixty-seven percent (67%).

In relation to this, it was found out that the most prevalent reasons for unemployment of the graduates of U-Pang are “no job opportunity” and “lack of work experience.” It was also determined that the waiting time for a graduate to land to a job is “half a month” to one (1) to six (6) months. It was recommended that the U-Pang should institutionalize a Job Placement Unit which will be placed under the Guidance Office or the Student Affairs Office. It is also strongly recommended that the institution should strengthen the On-the-Job Training (OJT) component of each program to provide more working experiences for its students.

Mugabushaka et al. (2003) traced those graduates from higher education institutions are frequently viewed as important tools for institutional development, particularly when the world of work is rapidly changing. The higher education institution can obtain systematic feedback from their former students using this strategy. Finding out where graduates are now, their employment situations, and their retrospective assessments of their courses of study could spark curricular debate and be highly fascinating for present or future students.

Albina and Sumagaysay (2020) added that the importance of tracer study is that it is a way of understanding the relevance and quality of programs being offered by universities as well as labor markets. This is very evident as tracer studies provides sufficient information to institution for them to identify several key factors and distinguishing attributes to evaluate the effectiveness and responsiveness of a program.

Based on the referenced tracer studies, the employment rate of the respondents gathered based on a specific academic year determined some factors that can be improved or conducted by institutions to enhance the employment rate of their graduates. Through the tracer study, recommendations were formulated that deemed necessary to address the external and internal factors that affect the performance of graduates in finding relevant jobs. Take the case of the Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Main Campus, Quezon City of which most graduates were not able to find a suitable job relevant to their completed academic program and through the tracer study, a recommendation was formulated that the CHED, together with the PRC, should encourage students to take the Professional Licensure Exam in relation to their degree program for them to easily find jobs relevant to what they have finished.

The purpose of this research is to engage in a destination survey of the graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts of St. Dominic College of Asia for Academic Years 2014-2016. Specifically, this study aimed to gather information and to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the graduates in terms of?
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Gender;
 - 1.3. Civil Status;
 - 1.4. Occupation; and
 - 1.5. Employment Status?
2. How long did it take for graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts of St. Dominic College of Asia to find a job after graduation?
3. What are the learning components in the curriculum that need to be strengthened and emphasized?

The study is limited only to the graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts from Academic Years 2014 to 2016. This tracer study also covered their demographic profile such as gender, age, and their employment profile. Lastly, this study also covered the skills related to the graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts, and determined the instructional skills embedded in the curriculum which can be enhanced furthermore.

This tracer study would be significant to the alumni office of St. Dominic College of Asia because it provides them feedback from the graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts. It will be of great importance to the dean because it serves as a good evaluation tool to determine the teaching learning factors that can be further improve within the degree program to make it more responsive. The findings of this tracer study provide awareness feedback to officials of SDCA pertinent to the Bachelor of Multimedia Arts program and the demands of the industries. This will apprise the teachers of their teaching efficiency, which will serve as the guide of the students whether to enroll or not in the course and to be able to anticipate their future employments status.

Conceptual Framework

In a study conducted by Kaijage (1998), findings revealed that the level and type of technical knowledge and skills required of graduates in the job market were related to the curriculum. This study's operational framework was conducted to trace and identify the employment status of graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts of St. Dominic College of Asia.

The paradigm of the operational framework of this tracer study is composed of three stages the input, process, and output. The input phase includes the graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts of St. Dominic College of Asia. Secondly, the process phase covers the data gathering procedures such as distribution of online questionnaire and answered through online.

Lastly, the output phase involves the occupation, trainings, and seminars attended after graduation, employment status, number of promotions during employment, monthly salary, job performance and satisfaction, problems encountered during employment, skills in the curriculum that needs to be strengthened or enhanced, and on-the-job training.

Figure 1. Research paradigm

Methodology

Research Design

This research study utilized a descriptive research design to provide specific answers associated with the problem specified in this research study. Descriptive research is useful in investigating educational problems. Descriptive research, according to Kelley et al. (2003), is useful in investigating educational problems, which is then conducted either through self-reports collected through questionnaires or interviews (person, phone, or online), or through observations, or through answering questions about opinions of people on a topic or issue.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the graduates of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts for Academic Years 2014 to 2016. A total of twenty (20) were determined from a population size of 51, equivalent to almost forty percent (40%) of the total population. The given sample of respondents was assumed to provide sufficient information which may not entirely cater the majority of the research population.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a questionnaire as the data gathering instrument to gather the necessary data and information to come up with accurate answers based on the provided statement of the problem. This research study on the other hand, provided the said questionnaire through online forms which could then be accomplished by the respondents via internet.

In validating the instrument, the adapted questionnaire was pre-tested to ten graduates of different colleges and universities who were not respondents of the study. Corrections, modifications, and validation of instrument were made with the help of the Alumni Head who also have the knowledge in conducting tracer study.

The questionnaire was composed of three (3) parts. The first part of the questionnaire gathered the demographic data of the respondents such as their name, address, email address, date of birth, telephone or mobile number, gender, and civil status. The second part of the questionnaire included the educational background of the respondents. This included the year they graduated from the program, and the postgraduate studies or advanced training they took right after graduation. The third part gathered the employment profile or data of the respondents, indicating the current job, position, and the length of tenure of the respondents.

The questionnaire also determined the graduate skills developed by the students through St. Dominic College of Asia. It also determined the possible factors or things that can still be enhanced on the program by gathering the recommendations and of the respondents of the study.

Results

The study showed the frequency and the distribution of the respondents of the study according to age. The findings revealed that 16 or 80 percent (80%) of the respondents were 22 to 24 years old and four (4) or twenty percent (20%) of the respondents were 25 to 27 years old. It was also noted that seven (7) or thirty-five percent (35%) of the respondents were females and the remaining thirteen (13) or sixty-five percent (65%) were males. Furthermore, eighteen (18) or ninety percent (90%) of the respondents were single, one (1) or five percent (5%) from the respondents was married, and one (1) or five percent (5%) was a single parent.

Moreover, the study also revealed that among the 20 respondents, 12 or 60 percent (60%) graduated in 2016, and eight (8) or 40 percent (40%) were graduates in 2015. Only one (1) or five (5) percent from the among the respondents said that they took another degree right after graduation, while the remaining 19 or 95 percent (95%) did not consider going to post-graduate degrees or advanced training after college.

With regards to employment profile, 19 or 95 percent (95%) from the respondents are currently employed and only one (1) or five (5) percent (5%) from the respondents is not. Among the employed graduates, 17 or 85 percent (85%) are working within Bacoor or nearby city; and two (2) or ten (10) percent (10%) are working overseas. Moreover, two (2) or ten (10) percent from the respondents are working under contractual basis; two (2) or ten (10) percent (10%) are working as probationary; 13 or 65 percent (65%) of the respondents are working as regular employees and two (2) or ten (10) percent (10%) are self-employed.

In addition to the employment profile of the graduates, all employed graduates were working on jobs related to fields under Bachelor of Multimedia Arts (e.g., Graphic Artists, Graphic Designers, Multimedia Specialists). The study also showed that fourteen (14) or seventy percent (70%) of the graduates said that their current job is also their first job after college; and five (5) or twenty-five percent (25%) from the graduates responded that their current job is not the first they had after college.

On the other hand, when asked why they stayed on their current job, eight (8) or forty percent (40%) of the respondents said that their reasons are the salary and benefits. Seven (7) or thirty-five percent (35%) among the respondents said that they are referred to career challenges. On the other hand, six (6) or thirty percent (3%) said that the reason why they stay on their current job is because it is related to their special skills; three (3) or fifteen percent (15%) said that their

current job is related to their course; and only one (1) or five percent (5%) of the respondents chose family/peer influence as the reason why they are staying on their current job.

Moreover, the study also asked for the reasons of the graduates on why they chose to change their job. The findings showed that four (4) or twenty percent (20%) responded that their reasons are salaries and benefits; and three (3) or fifteen percent (15%) from the respondents said that they are seeking for career challenge.

Findings also showed that two (2) or ten percent (10%) of the respondents stayed for seven (7) to eleven (11) months on their first job; two (2) or ten percent (10%) stayed for one (1) to two (2) years; and one (1) or five percent (5%) stayed for two (2) to less than three (3) years.

Furthermore, three (3) or fifteen percent (15%) from the respondents have been staying for one (1) to six (6) months on their current job; one (1) or five percent (5%) have been staying for almost seven (7) to eleven (11) months; ten (10) or fifty percent (50%) of the respondents have been staying on their current job for one (1) to less than two (2) years; two (2) or ten percent (10%) have been staying for two (2) to less than three (3) years; and two (2) or ten percent (10%) said that they have been staying on their current job for about three (3) to less than four (4) years.

In addition, seven (7) or thirty-five percent (35%) from the respondents said that they found their job through advertisement; three (3) or fifteen percent (15%) said that they applied as walk-in applicants; three (3) or fifteen percent (15%) said that they found their job through information provided by their relatives/friends; only one (1) or five (5%) percent responded that their job was recommended by someone; and three (3) or 15 percent (15%) responded “through other means” such as on-the-job training and own business.

The study also showed that eight (8) or forty percent (40%) of the respondents took less than a month to find a job; eight (8) or forty percent (40%) took one (1) to six (6) months; and one (1) or five (5%) percent took one (1) to less than two (2).

Among the respondents of the study, nineteen (19) or ninety-five percent (95%), who are currently working, responded that their college experience helped them in their present job. Findings also showed that ten (10) or fifty percent (50%) said that one of the most useful skills they learned in college was communication skills; eight (8) or forty percent (40%) responded “Human Relation Skills;” six (6) or thirty percent (30%) answered “Entrepreneurial Skills;” five (5) or twenty-five percent (25%) responded “Problem-solving Skills;” nine (9) or forty-five percent (45%) said “Critical Thinking Skills;” 17 or eighty-five percent (85%) answered with “Computer/Technology Skills;” 13 or sixty-five percent (65%) responded “Decision-making Skills;” and eight (8) or forty percent (40%) responded “Creativity/Creative Skills.”

Discussion and Conclusion

The study showed that most of the respondents are males and majority of them are singles. The findings also showed that only one of the respondents is unemployed, and this is because the respondents chose to study a second degree after college. On the other hand, all employed graduates are currently working with jobs related to fields of Multimedia Arts.

Furthermore, most of the respondents said their current job is their first job after college, and most of them considered their salary or benefits as one of the key factors on why they chose

to stay on their current job followed by career challenge and related skills. The study also showed that salary and benefits influenced the respondents on why they chose to find another job, followed by career challenge.

On the other hand, respondents said that they only stayed for about half a year to two (2) years in their first job before leaving. Moreover, most of the respondents have been staying on their present or current job for about one (1) to two (2) years.

Most of the respondents found their current job through advertisements and most of them took only less than one (1) to six (6) months before landing on their first job after graduation. Among the skills learned in college, the respondents found communication skills as one of the most useful skills learned in college followed by Critical-thinking, Human Relations, and Creative Skills.

Recommendations

St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA) intensifies its partnership with industries which will provide access to employment of graduates. The institution should focus and organize more job fair activities for the students of Bachelor of Multimedia Arts since the findings showed that one of the most determining factors in finding their jobs was through advertisements. It should implement the new BMMA Curriculum which underscores outcomes-based education specifically in instruction, research, and community engagement.

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